

Life Architecture Theory and its Industrialization

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Abstract: This paper provides an in-depth look at the origins of Life Architecture Theory, its core ideas, and its importance in the development of individuals and organizations. Life Architecture Theory is dedicated to providing scientific decision-making tools to help individuals plan and manage their life trajectories. The thesis details the ten core techniques of Life Architecture Theory, which cover a number of key aspects, from the meaning of life to the management of environment and health. Finally, the paper proposes specific steps and development paths for the industrialization of the Life Architecture, discusses how this theory can be transformed into an industry in practice, and looks forward to future development.

Keywords: Life Architecture Theory, Personal Development, Organizational Management, Meaning of Life, Decision Making Tools, Industrialization Path, Theory Application, Environmental Management, Health and Mental State, Research and Practice

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1. Origins of Life Architecture Theory

Human life is a short life, all people are equal from birth, but the unequal resources and strengths inherited from later life lead us to have different starting resources. We are in the process of making up for the differences in resources to understand the differentiated knowledge, a collection of different growth experience, with different resources we play different roles. It has always been a common pursuit for people to be crowned as king, to become famous, and to gain absolute power. Life structure theory is an important theoretical and guiding tool to provide scientific decision-making and life planning in this process.

Life Architecture Theory is a new direction in life science and human resources doctrine, a theoretical doctrine that studies the origin of human beings, the way they get along with the world, and their return, and an important tool that provides theoretical support for management and control among individuals, families, organizations, associations, and other independent bodies. The object of study of Life Architecture Theory is to take the individual as the starting point, covering families, organizations, associations, communities, companies, ethnic groups, political parties, and nations. Starting from the development and management of the individual, it extends to groups such as families, organizations, associations, communities, companies, nations, political parties, and countries. Doctrine itself to study the field of broad and specific, broad and unlimited is the life of the natural and social relationships are complex and varied, such as family relationships, friendships, work, man and nature, man and man, etc. These

complex relationships synthesized and in the life of the growth stage of the continuous superposition of the stages of development, in the various stages of growth, especially the early stages of growth, in the case of the original material environment is to live and learn things. Whether it is inheriting the existing resources or learning later, the elders or information controllers mainly adopt the model of life architecture theory to choose the information intake of the individual is particularly important. The core viewpoints of life architecture theory are material and environment, kinetic energy and information, and value output, and a life or an organization can be in an advantageous position if it has an advantage in several aspects. Through research and generalization, Life Architecture Theory concludes that through the scientific planning (selection) of self, elders, mentors, teachers, brothers, friends, etc., one can quickly become a "standard social person", and quickly profit from social rules to realize self-worth and achieve the purpose of life. Of course, life in practice is more complex, and the theory of life structure must be scientifically integrated with other disciplines, and work together with other life philosophies to structure life.

Life is the course of life from birth to death, covering the sum of relationships with society, nature, and the humanities; the survival of life is the foundation for the development of the life structure; the desire for self-growth and the accumulation of information given by other groups is the beginning of growth; the material and environmental synergy with the family serves as the starting point; and the theory of the life structure is the compass for the courageous advancement of life.

2 Ten Core Techniques of Life Architecture Theory

Life architecture theory (life architect theory) is based on the core arguments of life architecture, through the guidance of life architecture individuals, groups, organizations, etc. can make scientific decisions, realize the purpose of life, find the meaning of life, and obtain knowledge, wealth, honor, etc. based on the scientific and systematic management, guidance, and practice of life architecture theory. Life Architecture Theory believes that individuals can realize their own value and achieve self-worth through a certain period with the systematic help of life architects. Life, Learning, Home & Friends, Health Body & Warm Hearted, Skill, Rules & Creative, Information, Vision, Time & Space, Time & Time. vision, time & space, and environment are the ten core technology systems of the Life Architecture Theory.

Sifu is to respect life, cherish life, and grasp the value of life: the desire for life, the value of life in the "righteousness" and the "way" of the trade-offs; exhortation is to advise individuals to learn, to exhort groups, organizations, and the nation to learn culture, to pass on culture, to learn the basics, to learn natural sciences, to learn actively or passively. Natural science, active or passive learning, understanding of individual or organizational lack of knowledge, culture, always learning, endless learning; Friends of the family, have their own friends and family, for individual friends are their own like-minded, kindred spirits, partners, the family is the individual's initial is always accompanied by partners, for the group, the friend is the group with the same goal or resource collaboration, family groups are intimate groups, multi-group collaboration in order to maximize the value of life in the "Tao". Groups, multi-group collaboration in order to maximize the realization of the goal, to achieve the purpose; mind and body, healthy and good mental state and physical fitness is the foundation of the struggle, differentiated mental state and physical state will come up with a different model of growth in life, with other multi-systems in order to live long life and always win; good skills, people in the world, the group to establish the industry must have a strength, there is a skill, there are unique advantages, the process of having the skills is a difficult process! The process of having skills is a difficult process, which is an important step in career planning and life planning, and acquiring skills and receiving training in the process of career planning is the core process of good skills, and people's life is mainly based on good skills, and most of their lives (75%) are stayed at the level of good skills, and the combination of differentiated models of life can lead to a happy and satisfied life; the square and the circle, and the whole life of a human being is the process of dealing with the practice of the society, and it is a synthesis of the social relations, and

we have to abide by rules which are consistent with The rules of our own environment: the moral attributes of a particular environment, the rules of the organization, the rules of society, the legal rules of the environment, the rules under nature, the limitations of scientific theories, religion, authority and other rules of constraints, to comply with the rules is the first step in the behavior of the conduct of the first step, no rules, the world is chaotic, things do not work, no rules can not be square circle; letter theory, information systems theory, to do the decision-making systematization of the study, the life architects guidance Carrying out life architecture work requires information, life development index (CHEN LIFE INDEX) support, but also other systematic tools such as the MBTI, 16BF and other tools system support, as a systematic theory of life architecture theory also requires the support of information systems, systematic engineering, including engineering, informatics, cybernetics, philosophy, social, economic, political, cultural, psychological, behavioral, Neurology, pedagogy, etc., the important issues of life, schooling, career choice, family, career choices also need to be supported by a wealth of information; ambition, is the field of vision, is ambitious, vision of each person has, can be cultivated, the process takes time, the need for different time and space environment fostered, the vision of the ordinary person is a personal, is a family or a small organization with a long vision of the people with a large pattern, have seen the world colorful life, have seen the complex and ever-changing world, practice, and the world, and the world.

They have seen the complex and changing world, practiced a lot of things, things, the scale of affairs are very large, with a human vision, ethnic vision, etc., the cultivation of vision can be obtained through mentors, travel away from familiar environments, undertake large-scale projects, book reading, radio and television, the Internet, etc.; space and time, space and time is the existence of time and space support, we are in the context of a particular era, in accordance with the general trend of the era, in line with the nation, in line with the right of the clan, in line with the organization to advocate the trend of the cause and ideals, time is the most basic factor, is the timer of the life scale, but also to witness the core indicators of the key cause, treating the time to establish a goal, persistence; physical environment, is the basis of the environment, the environment from which we come, with the resources, the initial state of the genetic body state are unchangeable, the cognitive base are very different, the In order to better upward development, later with the development of life need to constantly optimize their own basic environment.

Life architecture focuses on guiding practice, life architect seekers and mentors are based on the life architecture theory and practice combined to guide life, guide life; for different life from the career dimension, role dimension, life segmentation dimension to deal with science, not mechanically, but flexible, specific case-specific analysis, combined with the scientific tools to deal

with; timely combination with practice, new doctrines, trends, to To make the theory of life structure everlastingly vitalized.

3 Life Architecture Industrialization and Its Steps

According to the Life Architecture Theory, Life Architecture requires the establishment of research institutes, professional holding companies, Life Architecture Industry Associations and other organizations, as well as the creation of newspapers, websites and other media to promote the Life Architecture cause; the establishment of research institutes, professional companies, the creation of websites and newspapers and the certification of Life Architects are the first step in the development of the Life Architecture industry; the establishment of professional associations, the profitability of professional companies of Life Architecture, and the standardization of the industry are the second step in the advancement of the Life Architecture industry; Life Architecture Theory has a global consensus, and its promotion is the third step. The globalization and promotion of Life Architecture theory is the third step; these three steps take a long time to take, and these three steps as a general program will take a hundred years or even more, and as a member or participant, these rules have to be obeyed.

A life architect is a person who agrees with the theory of life structure, has undergone systematic training and certification, and has the excellent qualities of a role model in terms of knowledge and professionalism. In the guidance practice, through the scientific tools of research and judgment of individual or organizational growth structure manual, life architects for professional interpretation, and in accordance with the theory of life structure to make scientific guidance, so that individuals in accordance with the theory of life structure to carry out life planning and life practice.

The life architecture industry is broad and specific. Broadly speaking, it involves life education, skills training, talent development, career planning, life planning, access to resources, reputation management, and so on. According to the industry attributes, it belongs to the "professional and technical services" category of the tertiary industry.

The main service objects of Life Architecture are school students, teachers, training structures, vocational colleges and universities, family parents, career confusion, life explorers, organizations and associations. According to China National Education Development Statistics Bulletin, the number of school students in China is currently 276 million, and the number of students is growing by 2% per year, China currently (2014) has about 430 million families, about 200 million white-collar workers, and there are 890 million Internet users in China. There are 890 million Internet users in China, with an annual growth rate of 3%; relying on Internet information technology means to find

information on life planning has become the mainstream, and personal vocational education, culture and entertainment, and life planning (clothing, skill enhancement, education, counseling, etc.) account for 23% of personal income; it can be predicted that the scale of the output value of China's life architecture industry will be at least 5.86 trillion U.S. dollars by 2020, and the world's life architecture industry is expected to be at least 5.86 trillion U.S. dollars by 2020. It can be estimated that the production value of China's life architecture industry will be at least 5.86 trillion dollars with the purchasing power of 2020, and the production value of the world's life architecture industry will be about 21 trillion dollars. Everyone needs a life structure once in his or her life.

The life architecture industry is not a completely innovative industry, it is an industry that has already existed stably but has been given new vitality. The education industry, career planning, career counseling, human resources, talent science, and vocational training in the current era (2020 A.D.) are all other industrialized manifestations of the specific life architecture.

In summary, the establishment of the Life Architecture Research Institute based on the Life Architecture Development Theory and the promotion of industrialized practice and development are the core objectives of Life Architecture.

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Author Contributions

All studies in this paper were conducted and headed by CHEN, Jianhua.

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